

Appendices

Appendix A: Uniaxial Tensile Testing of 3D-Printed PLA and TPU Specimens

This appendix details the procedures, equipment, specimen preparation, and results of tensile tests conducted to characterise the mechanical properties of FDM 3D-printed PLA and TPU materials. The experimental data obtained from these tests were subsequently used to calibrate the material models implemented in ABAQUS for the finite element simulations of the compliant revolute joints (CRJs).

A.1 Equipment and Experimental Conditions

All uniaxial tensile tests were conducted using a TA.HD Plus Texture Analyser equipped with a 50 kg load cell, as shown in Fig. A1. Axial tension was applied at a constant crosshead speed of 200 mm/min in accordance with the relevant ASTM standards for the tested materials.

Specimens were secured using screw-action mechanical grips. Although no specialised grips were employed for testing soft polymers, the TPU specimens remained adequately constrained throughout the loading process without observable slippage. All tests were performed at room temperature (approximately 23 °C) under ambient laboratory humidity, with no additional environmental control.

Strain was determined indirectly from the crosshead displacement recorded by the testing machine. Data acquisition and subsequent analysis were performed using Exponent software, the proprietary data-processing platform associated with the TA.HD plus system.

Figure A1. TA.HD plus Texture Analyser.

A.2 Specimen Standards and Preparation

In the absence of dedicated mechanical testing standards specifically developed for additively manufactured (AM) polymer materials, established international standards were adopted based on material classification and prevailing testing practice:

- TPU specimens were prepared in accordance with ASTM D412, a standard intended for the tensile testing of thermoplastic and vulcanised rubber materials.
- PLA specimens were fabricated following ASTM D638, which specifies tensile testing procedures for rigid and semi-rigid plastics.

All specimens were fabricated using an Ultimaker S3 FDM 3D printer, with printing parameters identical to those used for the CRJ prototypes to ensure consistency and minimise process-induced variability. The detailed specimen geometries are shown in Fig. A2(a) and Fig. A2(b). Furthermore, the print layer orientation within the gauge section was aligned parallel to the loading direction, ensuring that the applied tensile force acted along the deposited filaments rather than across the interlayer interfaces, which are typically the weakest regions in FDM-printed structures.

Figure A2. Geometry and dimensions of the tensile test specimens: **(a)** PLA specimen, and **(b)** TPU specimen.

A.3 Data Acquisition and Processing

Each specimen's initial gauge length (L_0), width (W_0) and thickness (d_0) were measured using a digital calliper. During testing, the tensile force (F) and crosshead displacement (ΔL) were continuously recorded by the Exponent software. The measured specimen dimensions and representative mechanical data are summarised in Table A1, while the corresponding load–displacement curves for the PLA and TPU specimens are presented in Figs. A3 and A4, respectively.

Table A1. Measured dimensions and key tensile test results.

Specimen ID	Initial gauge length L_0 (mm)	Thickness d_0 (mm)	Width W_0 (mm)	Cross-sectional area A_0 (mm ²)	Yield force F_y (N)	Crosshead displacement ΔL_y (mm)
PLA-1	20.00	4.1	6.5	26.65	1697	0.49
PLA-2	20.30	4.1	6.52	26.73	1636	0.51
PLA-3	20.10	4	6.53	26.12	1623	0.45
TPU-1	25.1	4.1	2	8.20	No Yield	-
TPU-2	25.1	4	2.2	8.80	No Yield	-
TPU-3	25	4	2.1	8.40	No Yield	-

Figure A3. Load–displacement curves of the PLA tensile test specimens.

Figure A4. Load–displacement curves of the TPU tensile test specimens.

The following expressions were employed to derive mechanical properties from the measured data:

- Engineering stress ($\sigma_{engineering}$) for PLA specimens was calculated using:

$$\sigma_{engineering} = \frac{F}{A_0} \quad (1)$$

- Engineering strain ($\varepsilon_{engineering}$) for PLA specimens was calculated using:

$$\varepsilon_{engineering} = \frac{\Delta L}{L_0} \quad (2)$$

- Yield stress (σ_y) for PLA specimens was determined via the 0.2% offset method.
- Young’s modulus (E) for PLA specimens was calculated from the slope of the linear elastic region of the engineering stress–strain curve.
- True stress (σ_{true}) and strain (ε_{true}): For TPU specimens, true stress and true strain were calculated from the engineering stress–strain data to more accurately capture the material’s behaviour under large deformations. Assuming volume constancy, true stress and strain are calculated using:

$$\sigma_{true} = \sigma_{engineering}(1 + \varepsilon_{engineering}) \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_{true} = \ln(1 + \varepsilon_{engineering}) \quad (4)$$

A.4 Results

Three specimens were tested for each material. All results were deemed valid and were included in the final analysis. Average stress-strain curve for PLA is presented in Figures A5.

Figure A5. Average engineering stress–strain curve for PLA (0.2% Offset Yield Method).

TPU exhibited nonlinear hyperelastic behaviour with no distinct yield point. True stress–true strain conversion was performed for accurate material modelling. Considering that the joints are not expected to undergo large deformations in service, only the initial segment of the average stress–strain curve was used for the material model. This region is illustrated in Figure A6.

Figure A6. Average true stress–strain curve for TPU.

All relevant mechanical properties—PLA’s Young’s modulus (E), yield stress (σ_y), plastic strain (ϵ_p), and the nominal stress–strain data (σ – ϵ) for TPU—are summarised in Table A2 below. These values serve directly as input parameters for the Abaqus FEA.

Table A2. Mechanical Properties of FDM-Printed PLA and TPU.

Material Properties (Mechanical)			
PLA	Elastic	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio
		2600	0.35
	Plastic	Yield Stress (MPa)	Plastic Strain (mm/mm)
		53.7	0.000
63.4		0.005	
		78.5	0.009
TPU	Hyperelastic	Nominal Stress (MPa)	Nominal Strain (mm/mm)
		0.0	0.0
		3.7	0.1
		5.3	0.2
		6.4	0.3
		7.3	0.4
		7.9	0.5
		8.3	0.6
		8.7	0.7
		9.1	0.8
		9.3	0.9
		9.6	1.0
		9.8	1.1
10.0	1.2		

Appendix B: Adhesive Bond Strength Tests

This appendix describes the experimental procedures and results used to characterise the interfacial strength of the bonded 3D-printed PLA–TPU interface. Two distinct loading configurations were investigated: uniaxial tensile loading and single-lap shear loading, corresponding to normal (t_{nn}) and shear (t_{ss}) traction components at the interface, respectively.

B.1 Specimen Preparation

As ASTM D638 and ASTM D5868 do not prescribe dimensions for the bonded interface area. Therefore, custom dimensions were designed for both test types in this study. The specimen geometries and bonded interface regions adopted for the tensile and single-lap shear tests are presented schematically in Figs. B1(a) and (b), respectively. All specimens were fabricated using an Ultimaker S3 3D printer, with PLA and TPU co-printed to form a direct bonded interface, without the use of any external adhesive. A total of five replicate specimens were produced for each test configuration.

Figure B1. Schematic illustrations of the bonded PLA–TPU specimens used for (a) tensile testing and (b) single-lap shear testing.

B.2 Testing Equipment and Experimental Conditions

All mechanical tests were conducted using a TA.HD plus Texture Analyser equipped with a 50 kg load cell. A constant crosshead speed of 5 mm/min was applied throughout the experiments. Tests were carried out under ambient laboratory conditions (23 °C). United testing screw-action grips were used to securely hold the specimens and prevent slippage during loading.

B.3 Data Acquisition and Processing

Prior to testing, the bonded width (W_{bond}) and bonded length (L_{bond}) of each specimen were measured using a digital calliper to determine the bonded area (A_{bond}). During mechanical testing, the applied load (F) was continuously recorded using the Exponent software integrated with the TA.HD Plus Texture Analyser. The resulting load–displacement curves for the uniaxial tensile and single-lap shear tests are presented in Figs. B2 and B3, respectively. The maximum loads (F_{max}) were subsequently extracted from these curves, and together with the measured bonded dimensions, are summarised in Table B1.

Figure B2. Load–displacement curves obtained from tensile testing of bonded PLA–TPU specimens.

Figure B3. Load–displacement curves obtained from single-lap shear testing of bonded PLA–TPU specimens.

Table B1. Measured bonded dimensions and maximum loads for tensile and shear specimens.

Specimen ID	Bonded width W_{bond} (mm)	Overlap length L_{bond} (mm)	Bonded area A_{bond} (mm ²)	Maximum load F_{max} (N)
Normal-1	5.1	10.2	52.0	223
Normal-2	5.4	10.2	55.1	330
Normal-3	5.1	10.3	52.5	270
Normal-4	5.2	10.1	52.5	249
Normal-5	5.1	10.1	51.5	274
Shear-1	6.3	10.2	64.3	399
Shear-2	6.4	10.1	64.6	362
Shear-3	6.1	10.1	61.6	426
Shear-4	6.1	10.2	62.2	404
Shear-5	6.1	10.1	61.6	316

The traction strengths (t) were calculated for both loading configurations using the following expression:

$$t = \frac{F_{max}}{A_{bond}} \quad (5)$$

This equation applies to both normal and shear loading cases, with only the direction of applied force differing between configurations.

B.4 Results

Five specimens were tested for each material. All results were deemed valid and were included in the final analysis. A summary of the calculated traction stress (t) is provided in Table B2.

Table B2. Summary of adhesive bond strength test results.

	Traction Stress (t)	
	Normal Direction, t_{nn}	Shear Direction, t_{ss}
Average (MPa)	5.1	6.1
Standard deviation	0.62	0.67
Coefficient of Variation (%)	13.2	10.3

Appendix C: Fracture Energy Test

This appendix describes the experimental procedures and results used to characterise the interfacial fracture energies of the bonded 3D-printed PLA–TPU interface under Mode I, Mode II, and mixed-mode loading conditions. Three distinct loading configurations were investigated: the double cantilever beam (DCB) test for Mode I fracture, the end-notched flexure (ENF) test for Mode II fracture, and the mixed-mode bending (MMB) test for combined Mode I/II loading, corresponding to the fracture energy components G_I , G_{II} , and mixed-mode $G_{I/II}$, respectively.

C.1 Specimen Preparation

C.1.1 End-Notched Flexure (ENF) specimen

The standard ENF specimen design, as specified in ASTM D7905, was initially considered but found to be unsuitable for PLA–TPU systems. Premature failure consistently occurred within the PLA section due to its brittle nature, preventing the initiation of interfacial delamination. This behaviour contrasted with TPU’s high compliance, resulting in a non-ideal failure mode.

Figure C1. Initial ENF Specimen Design.

To overcome this limitation, a modified ENF specimen was developed, as shown in Figure C2. In this configuration, the upper surface of the TPU (black) is bonded to the PLA (red) using a high-strength adhesive—significantly stronger than the bonding between the 3D-printed TPU and PLA interface. This adhesive interface is indicated by the blue dashed lines. As a result, when the specimen is subjected to shear loading, cracks are selectively initiated at the weaker 3D-printed interface, as shown by the yellow line.

Figure C2. Modified ENF Specimen Design for Inducing Delamination at the TPU-PLA Interface.

The modified specimens were fabricated using the Ultimaker S3 printer, with printing parameters kept identical to those used for the CRJ prototypes, and were subsequently tested under three-point bending, as illustrated in Figure C3, using a TA.HD plus Texture Analyser. The key specimen dimensions used for these tests are summarised in Table C1.

Figure C3. Schematic of ENF specimen geometry and loading configuration.

C.1.2 Double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen

The DCB specimens had a similar overall geometry and PLA–TPU bonded interface to the modified ENF samples but were equipped with loading blocks to enable tensile Mode I opening, as shown in Fig. C3. The corresponding specimen dimensions are also listed in Table C3.

Figure C3. Schematic of DCB specimen geometry and loading configuration.

C 1.3 Mixed-Mode Bending (MMB) Apparatus and Specimen Configuration

The MMB specimens had a similar overall geometry and PLA–TPU bonded interface to the DCB samples. However, unlike the DCB and ENF tests, the MMB test applies a controlled combination of Mode I (opening) and Mode II (shearing) loading, which cannot be achieved using a standard uniaxial testing machine. Therefore, a superposed lever system was employed. In this setup, specimens were subjected to simultaneous tensile and shear forces via a yoke and lever mechanism. The applied force was distributed along the lever arm (length c), generating both normal and shear loading components at the crack tip. The dimensions of the lever system are illustrated schematically in Figure C4. The key specimen dimensions used for these tests are summarised in Table C1.

Figure C4. Schematic of the MMB lever-arm loading system and specimen configuration.

Table C1. Geometric dimensions of ENF, DCB and MMB specimens used in fracture tests.

Test Type	Specimen ID	Thickness h (mm)	Half Span L (mm)	Width B (mm)	Crack Length a_0 (mm)	Young's modulus E (MPa)
DCB	DCB (1)	2.1	-	15.1	15	2600
	DCB (2)	2	-	15.2	14.9	
	DCB (3)	2.1	-	15	14.8	
	DCB (4)	2	-	15	15	
	DCB (5)	2	-	15.1	15.1	
ENF	ENF (1)	2.1	26.5	13	10	2600
	ENF (2)	2	26.7	13	10	
	ENF (3)	2.2	26.5	13.1	10	
	ENF (4)	2	26.5	13	10.3	
	ENF (5)	2	26.6	13.1	10.2	
MMB	MMB (1)	2.1	40.1	13.2	14.9	2600
	MMB (2)	2	40	13	14.8	
	MMB (3)	2	40	13	14.8	
	MMB (4)	2.1	40.1	13	14.9	
	MMB (5)	2	40	13.1	15.2	

C.2 Testing Equipment and Experimental Conditions

All tests were carried out using a TA.HDplus Texture Analyser fitted with a 50 kg load cell. The test procedure was displacement-controlled, with a crosshead rate of 1 mm/min. Testing was conducted under ambient laboratory conditions (23 °C), without environmental or humidity control. The load was applied symmetrically through the bonded interface to achieve Mode I, Mode II, or mixed-mode delamination as required.

For the DCB tests, the specimens were loaded via piano hinges to allow free rotation during opening, thereby promoting pure Mode I interfacial fracture (Fig. C5a). For the ENF tests, the specimens were positioned on a three-point bending fixture to induce Mode II-dominated loading conditions (Fig. C5b). The MMB tests employed a lever-arm loading system designed to apply a controlled combination of Mode I and Mode II loading at the bonded interface (Fig. C5c).

Figure C5. Experimental setups used for interfacial fracture testing: (a) Mode I DCB test, (b) Mode II ENF test, and (c) MMB test.

C.3 Data Acquisition and Processing

The following procedure was intended to extract fracture energy values from the experimental load–displacement data obtained in the DCB, ENF, and MMB tests. For each test type, data points were to be recorded at defined crack length increments and used to calculate the corresponding fracture energy. The general processing method can be outlined as follows:

- Record crack propagation lengths: Start from the initial pre-crack length a_0 . Each time the crack length increases by 1 mm, record the corresponding point on the load–displacement curve, up to a delamination length of 5 mm.
- Calculate fracture energy: For each increment, calculate the fracture energy (G) using the corresponding applied load (P) and displacement (δ).
- Plot the resistance curve (R-curve): Plot the fracture energy (G) versus the corresponding crack length (a) for each increment to determine the average fracture energy in the stable propagation region.

However, due to the absence of high-magnification imaging equipment and synchronisation tools, it was not feasible to accurately monitor the evolution of the crack tip during testing. To address this limitation and simplify the analysis, it was assumed that the fracture energy at crack initiation was representative of that during stable propagation. Consequently, the fracture energy was estimated using the maximum load (P) obtained from the load–displacement curve at the initial pre-crack length (a_0).

C.3.1 Mode I and Mode II Fracture Energy (G_I & G_{II})

Given the experimental constraints, particularly the inability to track incremental crack growth, the more precise methods recommended in ASTM D5528 and ASTM D7905, such as Compliance Calibration (CC), Modified Beam Theory (MBT), Modified Compliance Calibration (MCC), and Corrected Beam Theory (CBT), were not feasible, as these approaches require multiple crack length measurements for compliance calibration or effective crack length corrections. Therefore, elementary beam theory was adopted in this study due to its simplicity and well-established validity for beam-like specimens under quasi-static loading. This approach neglects shear deformations and rotational inertia, which is considered acceptable given the geometry and elastic behaviour of the tested specimens. Consequently, the energy release rates for Mode I (G_I) and Mode II (G_{II}) fracture were

estimated using expressions derived from elementary beam theory, applied respectively to the DCB and ENF configurations:

$$G_I = \frac{12a^2P^2}{B^2h^3E} \quad (6)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{9a^2P^2}{16B^2h^3E} \quad (7)$$

where P is the load, B is the width of the specimen, a is the corresponding crack length, E is the Young's modulus of the base PLA material and h is the thickness of a single beam arm.

C.3.2 BK Exponent (n)

The mixed-mode bending (MMB) test provides a means to determine the mixed-mode fracture behaviour necessary for evaluating the BK exponent (n). This test combines features of both the DCB and ENF configurations via a lever-arm loading apparatus, allowing the total applied load P to be decomposed into Mode I and Mode II components at the crack tip. The force distribution is given by:

$$P_I = \frac{3c - L}{4L} P \quad (8)$$

$$P_{II} = \frac{c + L}{L} P \quad (9)$$

where P_I and P_{II} represent the Mode I and Mode II loading contributions, respectively; L is half the span length of the specimen; P is the total applied load at the end of the lever arm; c is the distance from the applied load point to the lever pivot.

The total energy release rate (G_{total}) is then expressed as the sum of the individual mode contributions:

$$G_{total} = G_I + G_{II} \quad (10)$$

with:

$$G_I = \frac{12P_I^2a^2}{B^2h^3E}; \quad G_{II} = \frac{9a^2P_{II}^2}{16B^2h^3E} \quad (11)$$

The degree of mode mixity is quantified by the ratio:

$$\text{Mixed mode Ratio} = \frac{G_{II}}{G_{total}} \quad (12)$$

which indicates the relative contribution of shear to the overall fracture process, ranging from 0 in pure Mode I ($G_{II} = 0$) to 1 in pure Mode II ($G_I = 0$).

By performing pure Mode I, pure Mode II, and mixed-mode fracture tests, three corresponding mode ratios are obtained. These data points are then plotted on a graph of total fracture energy G_{total} versus the mode ratio G_{II}/G_{total} . A curve is then fitted through these three points using the BK criterion. The exponent of this fitted curve, known as the BK exponent

(n), characterises the relationship between the material's fracture energy and the ratio of Mode I to Mode II loading.

C.4 Results

Five specimens were tested for each material. However, additional tests were performed for the Mode I (DCB) and mixed-mode (MMB) configurations to compensate for irregular data observed in the initial specimens. The experimental load–displacement curves for the Mode I (DCB), Mode II (ENF), and mixed-mode (MMB) fracture tests are presented in Figure C6, and the corresponding calculated fracture energies are summarised in Table C2.

Figure C6. Load-displacement curves of (a) DCB tests; (b) ENF tests; (c) MMB tests.

Table C2. Summary of fracture energy values for DCB, ENF, and MMB tests.

Test Type	Specimen ID	Mode I fracture energy G_I (mJ)	Mode II fracture energy G_{II} (mJ)	Total fracture energy G_{total} (mJ)	Mode ratio G_{II}/G_T	Average (mJ)
DCB	DCB (1)	57	-	-	0	72
	DCB (2)	110	-	-	0	
	DCB (3)	65	-	-	0	
	DCB (4)	50	-	-	0	
	DCB (5)	76	-	-	0	
ENF	ENF (1)	-	110	-	1	102
	ENF (2)	-	86	-	1	
	ENF (3)	-	110	-	1	
	ENF (4)	-	92	-	1	
	ENF (5)	-	113	-	1	
MMB	MMB (1)	66	49	115	0.43	86
	MMB (2)	40	31	71	0.44	
	MMB (3)	49	37	86	0.43	
	MMB (4)	57	42	99	0.42	
	MMB (5)	33	25	58	0.43	

Figure C7. B-K Criterion Fitting for Mixed-Mode Fracture Energy.